

POLAC JOURNAL OF SOCIAL AND MANAGEMENT SCIENCES (PJSMS)

Vol. 3 No. 1 March, 2025

ISSN - Print: 2992-5009; Online: 2437-1246

Editor-in-Chief

Solomon Olubunmi, PhD

Editor

Samson Olowo Kolawole, PhD

Associate Editors

Vincent Okwudili Iweama, PhD
Nwachi Loveday Agwu, PhD
Ayogu Chiagolum Elochukwu
Shamsudeen Alhassan Musa
Sagir Lawal, PhD
Vahyala Adamu Tari, PhD
Ubong Evans Abraham, PhD
Kabiru Umar, PhD
Valentine Ayo Mebu, PhD
Ajene Sunday Apeh, PhD

Editorial Advisory Board

Prof. Benjamin Oladapo Olley,
Prof. Benjamin Oluwabunmi Omolayo
Prof. Mike Duru,
Prof. Abdullahi Hassan Gorondutse,
Prof. Hussaini Tukur Hassan,
Prof. Junaidu Muhammad Kurawa
Prof. Canice Esidene Erunke,
Prof. Ahmad Audu Maiyaki,
Prof. Zubairu Kwambo Dagona,
Prof. Abu Maji,
Dr Bello Halilu Rogo,
Dr Abdulrazaq Ibrahim

Interrogating the Forces of Cancelled Votes in the 2018 Gubernatorial Election in Osun State, Nigeria

POLAC Journal of
Social and Management Sciences
2025, Vol. 3 (1), 122 – 134
©Faculty of Social and Management Sciences
Nigeria Police Academy, Kano.
pjsms@gmail.com
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17683553

¹Ojo Olawale Ariyo, ²Odunayo Elizabeth Akomolafe & ³Leke Oke

¹Department of Political Science, Faculty of the Social Sciences, Federal University, Oye-Ekiti.
E-mail: ojo.ariyo@fuoye.edu.ng, +2347038898272

²Department of Peace and Conflict Studies, Faculty of the Social Sciences, Federal University, Oye-Ekiti, Nigeria.

Email: odunayo.akomolafe@fuoye.edu.ng, +2348065034232

³Department of Political Science, Faculty of the Social Sciences, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.

E-mail: lekeoke@yahoo.com, +2348033658474

Abstract

The paper investigated the ramifications of nullified votes in the 2018 Osun State Gubernatorial Election. A qualitative research framework was utilised for this scholarly investigation. Respondents' opinions were purposively sampled from four local government areas where cancelled votes were prevalent during the 2018 gubernatorial election in the state. Eight participants were drawn up and interviewed through in-depth interviews. The interview was validated using a Focus Group Interview (FGI) to allow a wide range of responses on the subject matter. Six officials from the People's Democratic Party (PDP), the All Progressive Congress (APC), the Independent National Electoral Commission, the National Orientation Agency, and two civil society organizations were interviewed. Fourteen participants were interviewed, transcribed, and analyzed using thematic analysis. The opinions of the respondents were correlated with the expectancy theoretical approach. The study discovered that cancelled votes were antithetical to the gubernatorial election. The contributing factors include perpetual fear resulting from security invasion, violence, illiteracy, and the official declaration of votes as cancelled votes by the electoral umpire. The study recommends intensive and effective voter education to reduce the prevalence of cancelled votes in Nigerian elections.

Keywords: Elections, cancelled votes, gubernatorial election, credibility, and violence.

Article history:

Received: 17 February 2024

Reviewed: 20 February 2025

Accepted: 29 March 2025

About the Journal: PJSMS is a multidisciplinary journal and the official journal of the Faculty of Social and Management Sciences, Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil-Kano, Nigeria, published biannually.

Ariyo, O. O., Komolafe, O. E. & Oke, L. (2025).

Interrogating the Forces of Cancelled Votes in the 2018 Gubernatorial Election in Osun State, Nigeria**Introduction**

In contemporary democracies, elections have emerged as a pivotal mechanism for the selection of representatives, with competitiveness serving as a hallmark of this process. The competitive nature of elections is characterised by the provision of equitable and reasonable opportunities for citizens to vie for governmental positions (Omilusi, 2017). This political competition stands as a crucial element of elections, reflecting the collective will of the populace. Following the commencement of Nigeria's Fourth Republic in 1999, the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) has orchestrated seven general elections: in 1999, 2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019, and 2023. Additionally, INEC has overseen various off-cycle elections in states such as Osun, Ekiti, Ondo, Edo, Bayelsa, and Kogi. These electoral processes have been marred by challenges, including diminished voter participation, electoral fraud, violence associated with elections, and a significant number of invalidated ballots (Awariefe & Nana, 2020).

The 2018 Osun State gubernatorial election is one of the most talked about off-cycle elections in Nigeria because the indecisive electoral contest caused by cancelled votes (Akinrefon, 2018). Cancelled votes are annulled by electoral officials due to irregularities or anomalies observed during the election. The Electoral Act (2022) stipulates in Section 53 that a vote shall be deemed null and void in two circumstances: firstly, when the quantity of ballots cast in a polling unit surpasses the number of registered voters, a phenomenon known as over-voting, prompting the election official to annul the results for that specific unit. Secondly, the election outcome remains undetermined until a fresh poll is conducted in

the affected area. Moreover, Section 36 of the aforementioned Act corroborates that the nullification of an election in a polling unit or primary may occur due to security concerns or the demise of a candidate. In such instances, the election results are withheld pending the electoral body's designation of an alternative polling date.

The Osun State gubernatorial election was held on September 22, 2018; during the announcement of the electoral outcome, the State Returning Officer of INEC nullified the results from seven polling stations spanning four local government areas within the State. As a consequence, the election was officially declared inconclusive (Abegunde & Awotunde, 2023). The indecisive electoral contest was premised on cancelled votes that exceeded the margin of votes (353 votes) between the two leading political parties: PDP, Senator Ademola Adeleke, 254,698 votes and APC, Alhaji Gboyega Oyetola, 254,345 votes (Akinrefon, 2018).

The cancellation of elections in seven polling units, which collectively comprised 3,498 registered voters, necessitated a supplementary election on 27th September, 2018, as this figure surpassed the margin between the two leading candidates (Akinrefon, 2018). Abegunde and Awotunde (2023) report that this supplementary election took place across seven polling units within four local government areas: Ife South Ward 8, Unit 10; Ife South Ward 7, Unit 12; Orolu Ward 9, Unit 3; Orolu Ward 8, Unit 1; Orolu Ward 8, Unit 4; Osogbo LGA Ward 5, Unit 17; and Ife North LG, Ward 10, Polling Unit 2, Oyere II. Despite the electoral commission's declaration of this contest as inconclusive due to cancelled votes, there exists a paucity of academic literature examining the Osun State gubernatorial

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

election in the context of standalone elections in Nigeria.

There is evidence in the global literature on the reasons for ballots being rejected or cancelled (Bassy, 2011; Van-Gyampo, 2009; Martins, 2017; Alvavez, Pettigrew, Stewart, & Wimpy, 2020), and few studies have investigated the reasons for cancelling votes and their impacts in elections (Hansen, 2000; Keeling, 2024). Scant evidence in the literature on gubernatorial elections in Osun State, Nigeria (Ayobolu, 2022; Abegunde & Awotunde, 2023) has only studied the impact of the indecisive nature of elections in Nigeria with reference to Osun State. However, researchers have not really investigated the underlying reason for inconclusive elections, which were cancelled votes, and their impact on the electoral contest in Nigeria, especially Osun State 2018 gubernatorial elections. Meanwhile, Akinrefon's (2018) essay realigned cases of inconclusive elections to rejected ballots at the 2018 gubernatorial poll in Osun State. Most scholarly literature is preoccupied with voided ballots at the poll due to a lack of sensitization, poor ink used, double thumb printing, and cases of protest votes, which are quite different from cancelled votes (Van-Gyampo, 2009; Ibeanu and Orji, 2014; Martins, 2017; Awariefe and Nana, 2020). While studies on rejected ballots have interesting findings on their impacts on Nigerian elections that are relevant to this research, most literature and scholarly reports in Nigeria have scarcely discussed the factors responsible for cancelled votes and their attendant implications on gubernatorial elections. Hence, this study focuses on the causes and implications of cancelled votes in the 2018 gubernatorial elections in Osun State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Elections constitute a competitive mechanism through which citizens select their

representatives in governance (Oduote, 2014). This process encompasses three crucial elements: vigorous competition amongst political parties, civic engagement in political activities, and a credible, trustworthy electoral system. Wojtasik (2014) delineated elections as a distinctive democratic procedure for appointing individuals to political offices or other positions via voting, highlighting salient features such as the uncertainty of outcomes, which are predominantly contingent upon voters' choices. This process facilitates governmental transitions (leadership succession), fosters responsive and accountable governance, and bestows legitimacy upon leaders who emerge victorious through majority support.

Kolawole (1997) opined that election provides a forum for citizens to exercise their civil rights by electing their representative through a competitive and transparent process. He added that such a process would allow the electorate to be enlightened on a wide range of political campaigns on issues related to elections and public policy. Akinola (2018) saw an election as a formal process of selecting a person for a public office by a ballot and making a choice between alternatives. He further sees electoral fraud or malpractices as improper, illegal, deceitful or immoral behaviour and conduct which affects the transparent electoral process. Gwinn and Norton (1992) described an election as the formal process of selecting a person for public office or accepting a political position by voting. The basis of these above definitions is to choose a leader by the decisions of citizens through ballots in a transparent, competitive and multiparty system. In essence, a credible election constitutes a peaceful means of political succession.

Joseph (1999) described elections in African countries as a means of legitimating the incumbent government since power change is

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

always difficult, as losing elections is compared to losing life. The scholar's view was that elections are mere statements without influence on the public authority because the incumbent could not tolerate losing the election. Joseph asserts that African elections are now endangered with despotic competition and renewal of tenure, and tolerance of the authoritarian government. Nigeria is not exempted as elections are held periodically every four years to elect the President, key executive and legislative officials locally, in all the states and nationwide. However, the election is characterised by the manufacturing of figures unrelated to ballots, low turnout of voters and election-related violence. The flaws and irregularities in the electoral processes negatively impacted not only the outcome of an election but also the integrity of the election management bodies in Nigeria (Olugbenga, 2007).

However, with the exemption of isolated cases of Nigeria's Gubernatorial Elections that were being supervised by large security personnel in Ekiti State, Osun State, Edo State, Ondo State and Anambra State; elections in the country have rarely been peaceful; they have become a matter of conflict that resulted not only in killings, maiming, and destruction of property but also in the death of the electorate (Olaniyan and Amao, 2015). Even the integrity of the electoral system is questionable due to electoral apathy and election-related violence, as past elections have revealed that citizens' interest is low in voter registration and turnout for elections in the country (Odusote, 2014). The citizens' irresponsibility and apathy have constituted setbacks for the credibility of the election in the country. Hence, for Nigeria's elections to be truly free and transparent, there must be freedom to advocate, associate, contest, and campaign. It also entails a fair and non-partisan Election Management Body, a

widely disputed resolution system, equal access to mass media and independent vote monitoring (Ariyo & Fasunwon, 2022). Scholarly literature on Nigeria's electoral system is extensive (Olugbenga, 2007; Odusote, 2014; Omilusi, 2017; Ayobolu, 2022), with few studies examined the impacts of cancelled votes on the electoral system. Most of the studies on cancelled votes are Eurocentric. For instance, in a study of the 2011 Portuguese legislative elections, Martins (2017) investigated the relationship between unconfirmed voting choices and blank ballots. The findings revealed that economic hardship and unemployment were significant factors in explaining the variations in blank votes within urban areas, which are typically inhabited by politically astute voters (Martins, 2017).

Toscano (2021) showed consistency in the number of cancelled ballots in black-dominated counties due to perceived discrimination. He concluded that such massive votes posed a great danger to the legitimacy of the US Election and the disenfranchisement of the black populace. Driscoll and Nelson (2014) discussed how invalid ballots were used as protest votes to improve parties' accountability and transparency by forcing them to self-reform.

Power and Garand (2007) explored how voters' distractions by parties' faithfulness led to large quantities of rejected votes in Latin America, with most votes voluntarily cancelled. An examination of the impact of rejected ballots on the outcomes of Ghana's Presidential Elections between 1992 and 2008 was conducted by Van-Gyampo (2009). The research revealed substantial evidence that the high number of rejected ballots influenced the results of the 2000 and 2008 elections. Van-Gyampo (2009) contended that a reduction in rejected ballots could have obviated the necessity for a second-round election, thus conserving financial resources and alleviating

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

the three-week period of political tension between the two primary contenders in the Presidential Polls.

Hansen (2000) showed evidence of inconsistency in rejected votes counted in the 2000 United States presidential election, which led to a recount of the election. The impact of voting in elections negatively affects the two candidates. The two candidates' votes, Gore (4,270) and Bush (17,710), were rejected because of over-voting (Hansen, 2000). He highlighted the factors that contributed to the incidence, including the high percentage of the elderly, black Hispanics, and college education, with a median household income. The election was considered inconsistent with the high percentage of household income and education for citizens (Hansen, 2000). There is insufficient global literature on the causes of cancelled votes. Few studies in this area of research have tended towards the indecisive nature of election outcomes in Nigeria. Akinrefon (2018) investigated the basis for the rejected ballot in the gubernatorial election in Osun State. This essay outlined the major activities of the indecisive election outcomes in Osun State without reference to the votes that were cancelled during the 2018 gubernatorial election. Similarly, Abegunde and Awotunde (2023) examined the process, conduct, and outcomes of the 2018 gubernatorial elections in Osun State and how they had a far-reaching impact on electoral management. The study revealed that the election was conducted with a predetermined conclusion, and it was marred by violence, intimidation, pressure, and agitation due to over-militarization. However, the study did not buttress the impact of the cancelled votes in the election, but aligned that the standalone election was a stalemate. However, there is scant literature within the African setting, especially in Nigeria, that has researched the impacts of cancelled votes on the outcomes of

the Osun State governorship election. A few studies that buttressed rejected ballots (Akinrefon, 2018; Adegboyega, 2019; Awariefe & Nana, 2020). Hence, this study aims to fill this gap by interrogating the forces of cancelled ballots in the 2018 gubernatorial elections in Osun State, Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework:

Expectancy Theory

In 1978, Victor Vroom introduced expectancy theory, which postulates that an individual's inclination to behave in a specific manner is influenced by the perceived likelihood of a particular outcome and its appeal to the person (Okojie, Aderotimi & Ogunmola, 1999). This concept suggests that political actors are driven to perform when they anticipate substantial rewards for their efforts (Glueck, 1980). The theory proposes four key elements: (i) political stakeholders' electoral performance is linked to achieving desired outcomes; (ii) these outcomes may encompass changes in status, position, recognition, compensation, or political appointments; (iii) political stakeholders believe in their capacity to exert sufficient effort to secure victory or leadership in polls, meeting expected performance levels; and (iv) political stakeholders prioritise the potential rewards associated with the anticipated level of performance over the challenges inherent in achieving it (Glueck, 1980).

The importance of this theory to the political discourse is that it explicitly explains the political behaviour of the party stakeholders in the election, as they would be motivated by the variance of political appointment, promotion, pay, contract, and other rewarding outcomes. Therefore, any factor that might hinder the outcome may be eliminated. The motivation for political stakeholders is expectation and not the process for achieving the goal. The strength of a political stakeholder is therefore dependent on how

strongly he can malign his polling unit or ward with his effort to achieve the desired performance (effort—performance). The theory was criticized for being too dormant, as it believed that all political stakeholders and the electorate are rational in making decisions, in which the stakeholders might have different levels of performance and expected high rewards. In addition, performance might be difficult to measure for a leader because of inadequate communication, lack of goal alignment, or leadership perception of the individual.

Methodology

This study used a qualitative methodological approach. Participants were strategically chosen from four local governments where vote cancellations were significant during the 2018 Osun State gubernatorial election. Eight individuals were selected for in-depth interviews. To ensure validity and capture a diverse range of perspectives on the subject, focus group interviews (FGI) were conducted. The study included interviews with six officials representing the People's Democratic Party (PDP), the All Progressive Congress (APC), the Independent National Electoral Commission, the National Orientation Agency, and two civil society organisations. In total, 14 participants' responses were recorded, transcribed, and subjected to thematic analysis.

Data Presentation, Data Analysis and Discussion of Findings

This section presents the qualitative findings obtained through comprehensive interviews and Focus Group discussions.

Factors Contributing to Ballot Cancellations in the 2018 Osun State Gubernatorial Election

An examination of the circumstances leading to the nullification of votes in seven polling stations spanning four local government areas

ultimately resulted in the 2018 Osun State gubernatorial election being deemed inconclusive. Respondents and scholars have identified some of the factors responsible for the spate of cancelled votes recorded during the election. These include illiteracy, over-voting, violence, and the undue influence of the military on voters.

Illiteracy and inexperienced first-time voters

One interviewee noted the following:

The percentage of mass political illiteracy in the state is alarming; I mean, those who show little or no interest in political issues. Uneducated people were mobilized to vote. Voters were paid to vote. Many of these people could not identify the party's symbols or the candidate's name. Many of these voters voted twice because of the money they received, which led to overvoting at the polling station.

Interestingly, some of the respondents linked the case of cancelled votes in the gubernatorial election to illiteracy, inadequate sensitization of voters, proliferation of registered political parties, and voter inducements during the election, which caused confusion or voter voting twice or more to receive monetary rewards. For instance, a respondent affirmed the following:

Vote-buying was alarming during the election period. Many voters sold their votes to the PDP during the election. However, when the APC came with a higher figure of N5000 instead of N2000 offered by the other party, in the process of satisfying the party agents because of the money they collected from both parties,; many voters were forced to collect ballot papers to vote, which was against the rule of single thumb-printing of a ballot for the same election.

Another respondent affirmed the following:

The first-time voter incorrectly voted twice in this polling unit.

They were not caught, and they did not inform them about the danger of over-voting.

In summary, the newly registered voters were either wrongfully informed about the danger of over-voting because they voted twice, and most people were also bribed by political stakeholders to win their polling unit at all costs. Ayobolu (2022) postulated that political figures and party loyalists engineered an atmosphere of turmoil to provoke violence in their opponents' strongholds, aiming to render the election inconclusive. This notion was reinforced by Van-Gyampo (2009), who highlighted the role of inadequate public education and widespread illiteracy in the nullification of ballots during Ghana's 2008 presidential elections. Superti (2015) proposed that uninformed voters were the primary factor behind ballot cancellations. The non-compliance and ignorance exhibited by the electorate, coupled with systemic challenges that hinder adaptation to new processes, present significant hurdles to electoral integrity. A study by Holt and Berens (2001) entitled "State Worst in Ballot Errors" demonstrated a connection between the inexperience of first-time voters and the invalidation of votes in America. The study found that newly registered voters were not sensitized to the voting process, resulting in ballot errors.

Uses of thugs and the military to snatch ballot boxes

The election in the same polling units was cancelled based on the expectations of the party faithful. This was corroborated by a respondent from the People's Democratic Party.

Many voters were chased away by the thugs. They are either scared of thugs or their past experiences with the government discouraged them from voting. However, many thugs persuaded to vote could not read or write. They were hired to intimidate

voters, steal ballot boxes, and wound people at the polling unit who wanted to resist them.

Another respondent noted the following:

The election was over-militarized by sponsored and counter-sponsored military personnel who assisted in the manipulation of the election. As noted by some of the respondents, some of the thugs connected with the military snatched ballot boxes, beat opposition, and created unrest in some of the polling units where the elections were cancelled.

The heavy presence of military personnel in polling units created panic among voters, causing them to vote incorrectly. Many of their party agents created confusion and disturbed voters. This was corroborated by the submission of Larmar (2024) that disenfranchisement is not due to any fault of the electorate, but of the government, political parties, candidates, security agents, and interested politicians who either attempt to frustrate an election or fail to take necessary steps to prevent such frustration, which could lead to the declaration of an election being inconclusive. Some acts that have led the INEC to declare an election inconclusive include the snatching of ballot boxes and massive violence at polling units.

Cancelled votes as a premeditated conclusion of the INEC.

Some respondents also accused the INEC of sabotaging the electoral process by aiding and abetting fraud in the election. The elections in the seven polling units were declared cancelled because it was a pre-determined conclusion for the electoral umpire to favour the ruling party. One of the scholars substantiated that the seven polling units where elections were re-run were a premeditated arrangement to declare APC in case they lost the election.

A voter who was a party stakeholder states the following:

The cancelled votes were officially pre-planned to favour the ruling party and their candidate.

Many respondents believed that there was no crisis at all in their polling unit to call for the cancellation of the 2018 gubernatorial election in Osun State. A few respondents noted that it was a party stakeholder resolution to cause chaos when their candidate did not win the election. This was corroborated by one of the officials of the National Orientation Agency in the State, who was interviewed in the 2018 gubernatorial election in Osun State:

In Ward 09, the Orolu Local Government, many polling units' votes were cancelled, and our staffers were in the town to educate the voters. The people were enlightened, but political parties were determined to truncate the people's will. Thus, this is not helpful and healthy for a viable democratic process, as the election was declared inconclusive and a rerun was conducted. Even so, we did not want a repeat of what happened in this local government to happen in any elections, either presidential or gubernatorial elections in the country.

One respondent confirmed the following:

Greediness causes this because voters want to collect money from different parties' agents and promise to vote for them. It should be checked.

By exploring the gap and unpreparedness of the electoral body, political gladiators created loopholes to undermine the electoral process and exploit the gaps in the electoral act to claim victory through the back door. The use of money to buy votes by political stakeholders from voters is to influence voting in favour of their candidates and to seek recognition, and as a means of influencing electoral outcomes. Lawler (1978) indicated that money is used as a social commodity to raise the self-esteem and recognition of

leaders. However, politicians/stakeholders can use money as bait to entice and encourage voters and thugs to perform their bidding in the election.

Similarly, one of the civil society organizations posited that:

There was a heavy presence of thugs, and they ransacked, maimed, and proudly said. Lack of proper orientation for the elderly and illiterate individuals could cause voided votes.

In support of the assertion that the electoral body orchestrated the nullification of votes and deliberately installed APC candidates as state governors, Azu (2019) examined the case of Orji Uzor Kalu, a former Abia State governor. INEC declared Kalu the elected senator, having secured 31,201 votes for the APC, thereby defeating the incumbent PDP Senator Mao Oluabunwa, who obtained 20,801 votes. Notably, 38,526 votes were annulled, a figure substantially exceeding the 10,400-vote margin between the two candidates. Paradoxically, despite utilizing identical electoral guidelines for the 2018 Osun State gubernatorial election, the electoral commission refrained from deeming the Abia North Senatorial election inconclusive (Azu, 2019). This discrepancy serves to illustrate the profound level of inconsistency and questionable practices exhibited by the nation's electoral arbiter.

Implication of Voided Votes on the 2018 Gubernatorial Election in Osun State

The implications of cancelled votes include the following:

1. Inconclusive election

The nullified vote bears considerable ramifications in the national electoral process. In the 2018 gubernatorial contest, a single-past-post electoral methodology was employed, whereby the victor was ascertained based on the candidate who amassed the greatest number of votes. Nevertheless, the

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

election was deemed inconclusive as the number of invalidated ballots surpassed the differential between the two foremost contenders. This outcome has a profound influence on a country's electoral framework.

As articulated by one respondent:

Researcher, what would you say about what happened in 2018 in the State of Osun Gubernatorial Election? Was it not because the votes were officially cancelled? That election had been won by Adeleke, but the INEC just came to tell us that certain wards' election was cancelled due to violence and a rerun election was conducted.

Another respondent noted the following:

The minimal proportion of invalidated ballots should not substantially alter electoral outcomes. The Osun populace conveyed their preferences through suffrage; nonetheless, there existed a desire for their favoured candidate to prevail, irrespective of circumstances. The constitutional authority of the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) to pronounce the election inconclusive merits scrutiny.

Thornton (1975) suggested that political malfeasance accounted for the elevated number of overvotes in the 1975 Boston mayoral election in the United States. In excess of 10,000 invalidated ballots, the mayoral contest significantly surpassed the margin between the incumbent, Kelvin White, and Senator Joseph Timilty, culminating in inconclusive elections and governmental alterations. These nullified votes precipitated an inconclusive gubernatorial election in Osun State in 2018. Notwithstanding the modest ratio of invalidated votes in the poll, this influenced electoral outcomes. The nullified votes reconfigured the electoral landscape in Nigeria and impacted election results. As one respondent remarked, "the people's choice was upturned with cancelled

votes." Lamar (2024) contended that Sen. Ademola Adeleke was the electorate's preferred candidate, given the considerable support he garnered from constituents in his state. However, the indeterminate nature of the election was underpinned by Regulation 44 (n) of the Approved Guidelines and Regulations for the Conduct of the 2015 elections, which stipulates that when the disparity between the frontrunner and runner-up is less than the number of nullified votes, the election is deemed inconclusive. The underlying rationale appears cogent, as the participation of disenfranchised voters might have yielded a different electoral outcome given that their number exceeded the margin between the two leading candidates. Hansen (2000) showed evidence of inconsistency in rejected votes counted in the 2000 United States presidential election, which led to a recount of the election. The impact of voting in elections negatively affects the two candidates. The two candidates' votes, Gore (4,270) and Bush (17,710), were rejected because of over-voting (Hansen, 2000). Ayobolu (2022) argued that the inconclusive election hampered the governance process in Nigeria, as it deprived citizens of qualified leaders to lead the state.

2. Increase in budgetary provision

The gubernatorial election in Osun State held on September 22, 2018, was declared inconclusive, and a rerun election was held on September 27th of the same year. The cancellation resulting in the n instance of this can be seen in the 2018 Gubernatorial Election in Osun State. One respondent stated the following:

Cancelled votes negatively affect the outcomes of elections in the state. This led to an increase in budgetary expenses in the election when it was declared inconclusive, leading to a rerun in the election. This further increased expenses on

the part of the INEC for the election.

The election defiled the budget of the electoral umpire by allowing the institution to plan additional expenses for the re-run election, which was not part of its initial plan. The re-run election opened another chapter in the annals of politics of Nigeria by defining constitutional provisions, electoral acts, and election guidelines that stipulated that when the margin between two leading candidates was less than the votes cancelled at the election, there would be the possibility of a runoff election. According to Van-Gyampo (2009), the reduction of rejected ballots could potentially circumvent the necessity for additional resource allocation in organizing a second round of elections for Ghana's premier political positions in 2000 and 2008. Moreover, such a reduction might have alleviated the three weeks characterised by heightened tension and political antagonism between the two foremost parties contesting the presidential elections.

3. It erodes the credibility of the electoral process in Nigeria

The majority of respondents attested that declaring the gubernatorial election inconclusive due to the cancelled votes has eroded the credibility of the electoral process in Nigeria and decreased the integrity of the electoral umpire. A respondent was of the opinion that:

There was tension and violence for the two weeks before the rerun election was conducted, thus increasing election insecurity and negatively affecting the election process.

A party stalwart stated the following:

People's choices suffer from defeat. The voters did not vote because of fear.

The cancelled votes created an atmosphere of militarization, a political climate, and an environment for the four local governments. It

also created an atmosphere in which citizens lived in perpetual fear due to the thugs and military invasions. The voters refused to come out, and vote during the election signified that they were scared of military invasion, untold happenings, and lockjaw. The people's choice leader was truncated by the ambit of cancelled votes. Hansen (2000) showed evidence of inconsistency in the spoiled votes counted in the 2000 US presidential election, which led to the recounting of the election. The impact of voting in elections negatively affects the two candidates. The two candidates' votes, Gore (4,270) and Bush (17,710), were rejected because of over-voting. Abah and Nwoku (2016) suggest that recurrent cancellations and subsequent election reruns have exposed inherent flaws and vulnerability to manipulation within the Nigerian electoral framework. The practice of declaring elections inconclusive because of cancelled votes has led to a significant erosion of public confidence in the electoral process. Ayobolu (2022) asserts that the nullification of elections in seven polling units has precipitated issues of legitimacy, diminished political trust, and widespread underdevelopment. An analysis of the rerun election outcomes revealed a notable level of voter disengagement across the seven polling units, which were distributed among the four local government areas within the state. One of the respondents noted that the cancelled votes contributed to the attendant low voter turnout in the rerun election because voters did not want a repeat of molestation suffered during the main election in the rerun election.

4. Election Insecurity

One respondent noted the following:

The week between the first main election and the rerun created tension in the town. There was a heavy presence of the military, as if we were at war with the State and Federal Governments.

A party stakeholder was of the opinion that:

During the rerun election, the opposition party denied access to the polling units. We were chased with the security and thugs. We could not vote again, even in the stronghold of the party.

However, the results from the polling units showed that in some of the polling units, the opposition party scored a ridiculous 2 votes and fewer than 50 votes in the rerun election. The result of the inconclusive election showed that the rerun election created confusion for candidates and citizens. It also created apathy because less than 50% of the total votes that were cancelled (1,485 votes) turned up in the seven polling units, against 3,498 total registered voters for the election. The inconclusive nature of the election, stemming from nullified votes, has fostered a misinformed populace and precipitated anxiety, detrimental political rivalry, electoral uncertainty, and prolonged legal disputes, thus negatively impacting the electoral process. The ensuing political unrest from the rerun election culminated in numerous fatalities among party adherents in the state. These observations align with Thornton (1975), who argued that corrupt political practices accounted for the substantial number of overvotes in the 1975 Boston mayoral election in the United States. The presence of over 10,000 invalid ballots in this mayoral contest significantly surpassed the margin between incumbent Kelvin White and Senator Joseph Timilty, resulting in an inconclusive outcome and subsequent governmental changes. Van-Gyampo's (2009) research corroborated the finding that rejected ballots in Ghana's 2000 and 2008 presidential polls led to a political party's ascension to power, owing to the consistent increase in presidential poll participation. This finding suggests that future elections should take into account voided votes on a national scale. While the issue of nullified votes was not exclusive to the Osun State election, it became

a topic of discourse due to INEC's adherence to its 2015 guidelines for indecisive election results in the country. Other states, including Anambra, Imo, and Kaduna, experienced similar inconclusive electoral contests during the 2019 general elections. Nevertheless, the nullified votes in the 2018 Osun State gubernatorial poll served to insulate the election umpire and compromised the transparency and credibility of the electoral process.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study attested to the level of uninformed electorates in the electoral processes that undermined the widespread irregularities and cancelled votes in gubernatorial elections. In addition, politicians sometimes misinformed the electorate of winning at all costs. They used different methods, including bribing election officials, buying votes, and causing insecurity through the creation of violence during elections. The pressure created by political stakeholders was to win elections through do-or-die affairs. The heavy presence of security personnel also hampered the electoral process by creating confusion and causing apathy in the re-run election. The findings of the study revealed that voters were not thoroughly sensitized to the rudiments of elections. Poor sensitization contributed to voters' inducements with attendant effects on society, including underdevelopment and corruptible government. The imperative for rigorous and sustained voter education, both during and beyond the electoral periods, cannot be overstated. This responsibility falls to the Independent National Electoral Commission, political parties, National Orientation Agency, and Civil Society Organizations. Such educational initiatives should emphasise the critical role of valid ballots in ensuring transparent, free, and fair elections. Moreover, it is crucial to implement a trial of electronic voting systems coupled

with comprehensive voter education programmes. This approach aims to reduce the occurrence of invalidated ballots, mitigate electoral violence, and combat voter apathy, thereby preventing these factors from exacerbating the challenges within the electoral process.

References

- Abah, E. O. & Nwokwu, P. M (2016). Inconclusive Elections in Nigerian Democracy: Causes and Cures. *African Journal of Politics and Administrative Studies*, 9 (1), 27-44
- Abegunde, O.; & Awotunde, O. (2023). Standalone election in Nigeria: The 2018 gubernatorial election in Osun State. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 7(1), 591-602.
- Adegboyega, A. (2019). History of rejected votes in Nigeria. Premium-times online media. Available at: www.premiumtimesng.com/features-and-intenews/179895.
- Akinola, A. (2018). Electoral Credibility and Money Politics in Nigeria: An Analysis of Ondo State 2016 Gubernatorial Election. *African Journal of Politics and Administration*, 1(1), 55-66.
- Akinrefon, A. (2018, September 23). Breaking: INEC declared that the Osun election was inconclusive. *Vanguard Newspaper*.
- Akintayo, U. (2015, October 15). Pastors fed on my sheep. Nigerian politics and the electoral process, any prospect. *Pastors Magazine*, 6.
- Aldashev, G. and Mastrobuon, G. (2010). Invalid Ballots and Electoral Competition. *Carlo Alberto Notebooks*, 15, 1-40.
- Alvavev, R., Pettigrew, S., and Wimpy, C. (2020). Abstention, protests, and residual votes in the 2016 election. *Social Science Quarterly*, 101(2), 925-959.
- Ariyo, O.O. & Fasunwon, A.F. (2022). Interrogating the forces of voter apathy in Nigeria's elections. *African Journal of Democracy and Election research*, 3(2), 59-85.
- Awariefe, C., and Nana, M.O. (2020). The Impact of Rejected Votes on 2019 Nigerian's Presidential Election: An Application of Ordinary Least Square. *International Journal of Advanced Research, Science, Technology and Engineering*, 6(4), 1426.
- Ayobolu, O. O. (2022). *A study of the implication of the 2018 inconclusive election in Osun State on electoral process in Nigeria*. Benin: University of Benin Printing Press.
- Azu, O.O. (2019, February 19). Lawyers Criticise 2019 Election postponement, Daily Trust, 14.
- Bassey, U., Noel, E., & Dike, O. A. (2011). Rejected votes from the 2011 presidential election in Nigeria. *A Proceeding of 35th Annual Conference of Nigerian Statistical Association held at Akure, Nigeria*, 341-348.
- Driscoll, A. and Nelson, M. J. (2014). Ignorance or opposition, blank and spoiled votes in low-information, highly politicized environments. *Political Research Quarterly*, 67(3): 547-561.
- Electoral Act 2022 (amended). Voided votes and declaration of results: Sections 2, 54, and 69.
- Glueck, W. (1980). *Management*. New York: Dryden Press.
- Gwinn, r. and Norton, P. (1992). *The New Encyclopaedia Britannica*. Chicago: Chicago University Press.
- Hansen, B.E. (2000). *A Nonparametric analysis of under-votes in the Palm Peach Presidential Vote: Implications of a recount*. Stockwell: Department of Economics, University of Wisconsin.
- Herron, M. C. and Sekhon, J. S. (2005). Black candidates and voters: Assessing the impact of candidate races on uncounted vote rates. *The Journal of Politics*, 67(1), 154-177.
- Holt, D. and Berens, M. J. (2001, April 29) State Worst in Ballot Errors. *Chicago Tribune*.
- Ibeanu, O. and Orji, N. (2014). *Approaches to civic and voter education: Nigeria's*

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

- experience in comparative perspective.*
Abuja: INEC.
- Joseph, R. (1999). *Democracy and Prebendal Politics in Nigeria: The Rise and Fall of the Second Republic.* Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Keeling, P. (2024). When the election was cancelled,
<https://democracyclub.org.uk/blog/2024/09/24/when-elections-are-cancelled/>
accessed on 24/1/2025.
- Kolawole, D. (ed.) (1997). *Reading in Political Science.* Ibadan: Dekaal Publisher
- Lamar, J. G. (2024) 2018 gubernatorial election in Osun State, Nigeria.
file:///C:/Users/HP/Downloads/Osun_Election_INECs_Inconclusiveness.pdf
accessed on 27/4/2024
- Martins, R. (2017). Blank and null: Examination of non-conventional voting choices. University of Coimbra: Centre for Business and Economic Research.
- Oduote, A. (2014). Nigerian democracy and electoral process since amalgamation: lessons from a turbulent past. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 19 (10), 25-38.
- Okojie, S.E., Aderotimi, E., & Ogunmola, J.O. (1999). *Management principles* (2). Akure: Stecom publishers.
- Okon, G.B. (2013). Voter Education by the Nigerian Broadcast Media: A Normative Appraisal of Three Radio Stations in the Port Harcourt Metropolis. *Journal of Media Studies*, Vol. 28(1), 57-81.
- Olaniyan, A.O. and Amao, O.B. (2015). Election as Warfare: Militarisation of Elections and the Challenges of Democratic Consolidation in Nigeria. *International Affairs Forum*, Spring 2015.
- Olugbenga, O.E. (2007). *Vote-Buying and Election Rigging in Nigerian Politics* in Omotoso, F. (ed.). *Readings in political Behaviour.* Ibadan: Johnmof Printer Ltd.
- Omilusi, M. (2017). *Your Vote or Your Life? Tracking the Intangible Dangers in Nigeria's Electoral Politics*, Ibadan: Stirling-Horden Publishers Ltd.
- Superti, C. (2015). Blank and null votes: An alternative form of democratic protest? London: Routledge.
- Thornton, M. (1975, November 6). *10,000 Boston Voters On Tuesday Left A Blank On Choice Of Mayor.* New York Times, 1-2.
- Toscano, J. (2021). *Whose ballots are rejected: Demographic dynamics of provisional ballots in North Carolina?* Durham N.C: Duke University.
- Van-Gyampo, R. E. (2009). Rejected ballots and democratic consolidation in Ghana's Fourth Republic. *An International Multi-Disciplinary Journal, Ethiopia* 3(3), 282-296.
- Wojtasik, W. (2014). Functions of Elections in Democratic Systems. *Political Preferences*, 25-29.